

Smart Rurality: Reconciling Convergence with Growth and Wellbeing at Local Level?

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Over the last ten years, smart rurality has earned a momentum among rural territories and communities, all the way up to becoming a hallmark for territorial marketing and distinctiveness. Rural actors have issued formal declarations (e.g. [Bled Declaration](#), [Smart Islands Declaration](#), [Smart Mountains Declaration](#)) to advocate for smart rural development as a path towards more territorially-just EU politics. Smart rurality has also become a popular concept into EU policymaking. Notably, since 2021, it has received a few dedicated funding, and was referenced in the key EU policies: the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and Cohesion Policy.

While rural communities and EU policymakers are united in recognizing smart rural development as a process *inherently beneficial and normatively desirable* for making rural Europe more prosperous, **several questions remain unanswered**. What does it mean to be a smart rural area? How does this concept can it bridge the urban-rural divide and address the so-called '[revenge of places that do not matter](#)'? Is smart rurality simply a new slogan against the panacea of a widening gap between rural and other territories or is it an auspice for integrated territorial development? This article provides an overview of Smart Rurality, its components, and how this concept is integrated into current EU policies and recommendations for the post-2027 policy discussions.

Smart Rurality

Smart rural communities are widely understood as territories and communities that build upon territorial strengths and assets to meet their own needs and improve their resilience and wellbeing. Smart rural areas are territories empowered and able to address urgent and often complex challenges, such as demographic change, service provision, and enhanced quality of life, which require multi-sectoral and multi-stakeholder interventions. For instance, the EU-funded [Interreg Alpine Smart Villages](#) project proposed a strategic approach to steer transition of the region by addressing economic globalisation, demographic trends, and climate and energy challenges all at the same time. Smart rural areas are characterised by a

more holistic, human-centric, and flexible approach, where community-solutions assume a bigger space than technological innovations.

In this framework, **rural smartification** – *understood as the transition towards smart rural areas* – is expected to deliver a wide range of benefits, from an optimised management of local resources (e.g. water, waste, electricity) to improved services (e.g. transport), real-time information mechanisms, enhanced wellbeing, and citizen empowerment. More widely, this transformation is progressively considered as the antechamber for revitalisation, attractiveness and sustainability in rural areas.

Key Components and Smartness Readiness Levels

While many are cheering 'smart rural areas', less clear is what makes a rural area become smart and how its level of smartness should be assessed. This **intended flexibility** aims to avoid imposing a 'dress too tight' on smart rurality, allowing rural communities to interpret it based on their own needs, specificities and wishes (in line with the principle of *place-based development* and *self-determination*).

Some scholars propose using the [six building blocks](#) of Smart Cities (People, Living, Governance, ICT, Environment, Energy, Economy) to guide smart rurality. Other conceptual and operational frameworks for smart rurality are considered by EU policymakers. For instance, the EU's Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas set out four pillars (Stronger, Connected, Prosperous and Resilient Rural Areas) for guiding rural development. Additional frameworks are currently being developed and tested, by EU-funded projects on Smart Villages (e.g., [SMART ERA](#), [FUTURAL](#), [RURACTIVE](#)). Thus far, the large majority suggested frameworks highlight the multi-sectoral nature of applications and strategies for driving rural smartification.

In this discussion of key components of Smart Rurality, Information and communication technology (ICT) is widely regarded as a key enabler of Smart

Rurality and often as a *'sine qua non'* condition for achieving it. It is important to note that **several scholars caution against assuming a direct causal relationship between digital transformation and smartification of rural communities**. In other words, digitalization does not necessarily make communities smart, and [scholars](#) argue of an existing **normative bias** in smart research.

Furthermore, some scholars argue that rural smartification can be triggered investing in a certain level of **technological, operational and environmental readiness**, denoting the presence of enabling characteristics which can facilitate rural areas to become 'smart'. For instance, broadband accessibility and electric reliability contribute unleashing a certain level of **technological readiness** which is instrumental to smart rurality. Certainty of funding instruments, commitment from the government and organisational capability increase the capacity of leading and delivering smart rurality (i.e. the **organisational readiness**). Last but not least, **environmental readiness**, intended as the existence of an enabling framework and ecosystem, depends upon factors such as third-part involvement, supportive policies and regulations, purchasing power of citizens for technology.

Overview of Smart Rurality History in the EU

At EU level, Smart Rurality began to substantially enter EU policy discussions with the [Cork Declaration 2.0 'A Better Life in Rural Areas'](#) (2016), which called for an EU-strategic approach to rural revitalisation ([European Parliament, 2021](#)). Following this declaration, a number of strategic documents and initiatives aimed at developing an EU approach to Smart Rurality, including the [EU Action for Smart Villages](#) and the [Smart eco-village project](#) (2017), the ENRD [thematic working group on Smart Villages](#) (201-2020) and the Smart Villages Platform, the Bled Declaration "[Smarter Villages for a Smarter Future of the Rural Areas in the EU](#)" (2020), [EU Startup Village Forum](#) (2021) and several EU-funded projects on smart rural development ([SMART Rural 21](#), [SMART Rural 27](#), [RURACTIVE](#), [FUTURAL](#), [SMARTERA](#)).

In 2021, the EU Commission recalled the attention on Europe's rural areas as backbone of the Union through its rich climatic, natural and cultural diversity and launched an ambitious plan to transition towards strong, connected, prosperous and resilient rural areas by 2040 with the [EU Long-Term Vision for EU's Rural Areas](#). This Strategy delivered [specific funds](#) to pilot smart rural solutions

and connect them to the LEADER/CLLD approach, in particular, under the pillar of 'Stronger Rural Areas'.

EU Policies Tackling Smart Rurality

Since 2021 the legislative foundations of both the Common Agricultural Policy and the Cohesion Policy (and particularly the ERDF) set up the possibility for the EU's Member States to design support measures for **Smart Villages**, a recent EU initiative to enhance smart rural development. However, a [country-by-country review](#) shows that only a few EU Member States incorporated Smart Villages in their CAP Strategic Plans beyond the LEADER approach, and none did so in their Cohesion Policy programmes. This means that, **according to the current architecture, the EU Member States have a significant role into designing support for rural smartification** through their CAP Strategic Plans and Operational Programmes, unfortunately this potential has been widely untapped in the current programming period.

Additionally, support to smart rural development can also be channelled through the **EU Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3)**, an instrument elaborated in early 2010s to deliver strong *regional innovation ecosystems*. Smart Specialisation Strategies are aimed at helping regions to identify and implement research and innovation activities in domains where they can excel and, since 2014, they are an **ex-ante conditionality for accessing EU Structural and Investment Funds**. Whereas these Strategies have the potential to boost smart rural development in some EU's regions, [some scholars](#) argue that their use for the benefits of rural areas has been quite restrained, and this instrument is not well suited to drive development of rural territories.

Last but not least, the concept of smart rurality in EU policies is strongly related to the **CLLD/LEADER approach**. Since early 90s, the CLLD/LEADER approach set up the EU's model for bottom-up local development through public-private partnerships and community engagement. Despite the scope of CLLD/LEADER and Smart Villages might seem to overlap, they are not. In fact, CLLD/LEADER should be understood as an umbrella instrument which can be used to fund Smart Villages strategies and solutions while also providing a wider territorial strategy to led local development. Additionally, compared to the CLLD/LEADER programme, Smart Villages are more limited in size (e.g. village), scope (i.e. local innovation and experimentation) and scale (small-scale actions).

Support to Smart Rurality in 2021-2027 EU Policies

In Europe, rural areas cover 80% of the overall surface and host 137 million people representing approximately a third of its population. Despite this, only 16% of the 2021-2027 EU Cohesion Policy funds are directly and explicitly allocated to rural areas, whereas more than 80% of the remaining shared management funds are not territorially targeted (EC, 2023). Furthermore, only 8% of the current 2023-2027 CAP allocations contribute to rural areas beyond farming (Ibid.).

Given the multi-sectoral and multi-disciplinary nature of Smart Rurality, other **sectoral EU policies** can contribute to deliver smart rural areas and communities. For this reason, the Table below illustrates an analysis of the contribution of EU policies to indicators for Rural Smartness' Readiness (Mukti *et al.*, 2021). By doing so, table 1 assesses how far selected current EU policies support the technological, organisational and environmental readiness to achieve smart rural areas.

Table 1. Analysis of policy support to the readiness of smart rural areas across EU 2021-2027 policies

Smart rurality Related main EU policies analysed	Contribution to Indicators for Rural Smartness' Readiness		
	Technological	Organisational	Environmental
Common Agricultural Policy	++	++	++
Cohesion Policy	++	++	++
EU Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas	++	++	++
EU Green Deal	+	+	+
Next Generation EU	+	+	+
New EU Global Health Strategy	-	+	+
EU Care Strategy	++	+	+
EU Pillar of Social Rights Action Plan	+	+	+
2030 Strategic Framework for Education and Training	-	+	+
EU Digital Education Action Plan	+	+	+
EU Data Strategy	+	+	+
EU Skills Agenda for sustainable competitiveness, fairness and resilience	-	+	+
New EU Innovation Agenda	+	+ / ++	+
EU Talent Booster Mechanism	++	++	++
Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy	+	+	++
EU Tourism Agenda 2030	-	+	+
EU Industrial Strategy	+	+	+
EU Biodiversity Strategy	-	++	+
EU Nature Restoration Law	-	++	+
EU Climate Adaptation Strategy	+	+ / ++	+
Farm to Fork Strategy	++	++	++
Bioeconomy strategy	-	+	+
Waste Framework Directive	-	+	+
Circular Economy Action Plan	-	+	+
SME Strategy for Sustainable and Digital Europe	-	+	-
eGovernment Action Plan	-	+	+
EU Strategy on Gender Equality	+	+	+
OVERALL SCORE contribution to readiness (per category)	41%	67%	63%

Conclusion

While representing 80% of EU's surface, rural areas have been long overlooked in European policies, and the gap with other territories has worryingly increased, as reported at repeated instances by the EU Commission in its yearly [Cohesion Reports](#). Smart Rurality is widely seen as an approach to be back on the track of EU's harmonious territorial development. Yet, Smart Rurality – to become an operational concept – needs to be supported by a common conceptual understanding and an enabling policy framework aimed at addressing simultaneously the technological, environmental and organisation readiness of rural areas.

As it appears from the analysis in Table 1, only a few policies aim at addressing at the same time technological, organisational and environmental readiness for Smart Rurality, (i.e. CAP, Cohesion Policy, EU's LTVRA, EU Talent Booster Mechanism and Farm to Fork Strategy). In most cases, specific measures for promoting technological, organisational and environmental readiness exist but are **not territorially targeted** (with the subsequent risk of benefit only urban areas) and/or they **lack measurable targets** with respect to rural territories. It emerges that Organisational Readiness received the highest score in analysed EU policies (present in 67% of analysed policies), followed by Environmental Readiness (63%), while Technological Readiness lags behind (41%).

It appears that the **least addressed** sub-indicators to achieve Smartness Readiness are (in order) *the Willingness of rural citizens to utilise IT services, Digital device ownership penetration, and Electric liability*. Whereas the most addressed sub-indicators are the ones on *Certainty of sustainable funding, Supportive regulation and policies, Organisation capability and collaboration*.

To support smart rural areas in view of the post-2027 EU Programming Period, it is crucial to:

- **Foresee targeted objectives, measures and investments for Smart Rurality** ([in line with Srsen CoR Opinion](#)), embedding them across all policies in compliance with the EU Better Regulation Agenda, Art. 174/175 of the Treaty of the Functioning of the EU, and, if needed, through the planning of specific earmarking, in a similar manner to which currently a minimum of 8% ERDF funds are allocated to urban development.
- **Ensure that measures and programmes supporting smart rural initiatives** (e.g. Smart Villages, Startup Villages) **are embedded into territorial schemes** sustaining development and innovation (e.g. CLLD/Leader, Smart Specialisation Strategies, Macro-regional strategies, Operational Programmes, National Plans) and hence contribute to the wider territorial innovation ecosystem and sustained attractiveness.
- **Ensure the issuance of small-scale innovation schemes** (e.g. Interreg Alpine Space small funds, Horizon Europe cascade funding), **simplified cost options** (e.g. Horizon Europe funds) and one-stop-shop platforms (e.g. Rural Toolkits) to facilitate local actors accessing and using funds for rural smartification.
- **Foster simultaneously the technological, organisational and environmental readiness of rural areas** to unlock the transition towards smart rural areas without disregarding sufficient support to basic technological needs of rural areas (i.e. broadband penetration, electric reliability, digital device ownership).
- **Don't forget the Focus on Social Innovation:** There is no proof of casual relation between technological innovation and transition to smart rural areas. Adequate focus should be given on social innovation and capacity building to support environmental and organisational readiness.

Disclaimer

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